

CAA SIG on "*Semantics and LOUD in Archaeology*"

Hic sunt dracones

#CAADataDragons

In historical maps, the phrase `Hic sunt dracones` (engl. here be dragons) is used to describe areas which were unknown to the cartographer. Today the WWW gives researchers the possibility of sharing their research (data) and enables the community to participate in the scientific discourse to create previously unknown knowledge. But much of this shared data are not findable or accessible, thus resulting in modern unknown data dragons. Often these data dragons lack connections to other datasets, i. e. they are not interoperable and in some cases even lack usefulness or usability. To overcome these shortcomings, a set of techniques, standards and recommendations can be used: Semantic Web and Linked Open Data, the FAIR principles and LOUD data.

LOUD and FAIR data in CAA context

Various researchers are doing modeling semantic information and producing Linked Data and LOUD according to the FAIR principles in any applications of archaeological data. Prominently the Numismatics Community (Ethan Gruber, David Wigg-Wolf, Karsten Tolle, ...) and the Pelagios Commons Community (Valeria Vitale, Leif Isaksen, ...) are forerunner in this case. Other researchers (Florian Thiery, Martina Trognitz, ...) of other institutions and subjects are also working on the LOD topic as well, also at the last CAAs. We would like to further establish Linked Data in archeology, enable beginners to use and produce Linked Data, invite other scientists for discussion, and embed LOD as an important topic through an SIG at the CAA conference and community.

Aims and Perspectives

The core aim of this group is to use the CAA's SIG format to raise the awareness of Linked Data in archaeology, this is to be achieved through some primary objectives:

- Create a friendly and open platform to discuss the role of LOUD and FAIR Data in archaeology.
- Enable the CAA community to get the LOD basics throughout workshops, teaching material, etc. > [@GaryNobles](#)
- Take on the challenge to develop LOUD publishing workflows in archaeology.
- Integrate the semantic modelling & ontology community (e.g. CIDOC CRM, SKOS, ...) and infrastructure community (Pelagios, Momisma, Wikidata, ...) into LOD in archaeology.
- Forge closer collaborations between researchers already active in this field and allow for the education of researchers and other interested parties.
- Provide a platform to present and evaluate the various avenues which are open to archaeology and LOD.
- Encourage development of related technologies, frameworks and theoretical perspectives.
- Point out and anchor the topic Data Quality in LOUD publishing.
- Strengthen the subject of LOD gazetteers for archaeological and ancient research > [@nottinauta](#)
- Strengthen the subject of LOD thesauri, e.g. Getty, Heritage England, ...

more aspects?

The group further respects the CAA's rules which govern Special interest groups as detailed here: <http://caa-international.org/special-interest-groups/>

Former related Activities at CAA

- Session on Ontologies at CAA Paris 2014 (S07 Ontologies and standards for improving interoperability of archaeological data: from models towards practical experiences in various contexts)
- Session on Linked Data at CAA Siena 2015 (S2D Linked Data: From interoperable to interoperating)
- Roundtable on Linked Data and Pottery at CAA Siena 2015 (RT5 Linked Open Data Applied to Pottery Databases)
- Session on Linked Data at CAA Oslo 2016 (S21 Linked Pasts: Connecting islands of content)
- Session on LOD and Data Quality at CAA Tübingen 2018 (S33 Guaranteeing data quality in archaeological Linked Open Data)
- Session on LOD and Data Quality at CAA Krakow 2019 (S14 Modelling Data Quality in archaeological Linked Open Data)

Proposed SIG Activities at CAA

LOUD SIG Roundtable at the next CAAs on LOD in archaeology

LOUD SIG Session at the next CAAs on Semantics / LOUD and FAIR data

SIG work for outreach

- The SIG wants to make the **Data Dragons** visible!

- Website <http://datadragon.link> to share all information on SIG activities and the LOUD and FAIR topic itself
- GitHub organisation <https://github.com/caa-datadragons> with SIG members as owner all others can pull requests

published LOD Cookbook for Beginners ("Pizza in the ancient Rome") like the [Protege](#) ;-)

Pizza Ontology

[@nottinauta](#)

published list of LOD in archaeology related infrastructures with its URI resources, sparql endpoints, APIs, dumps, etc. for Objects (Nomisma etc) Gazetteers (Pleiades etc) Thesuari (Getty etc) Time (ChronOntology etc) Persons (GND etc) GeoData (OpenStreeMap etc)

git repo (pull requests for edit/expand)

published list of LOD in archaeology related talks an papers

git repo (pull requests for edit/expand)

SIG Governance

The group was proposed at CAA 2019 in Krakow, it will be formed if consent is given by the CAA steering committee and it is ratified by the CAA membership at the Annual General Meeting at CAA 2020 in Oxford. Within a year the SIG will make arrangements to appoint a speaker, this person will cater for the day-to-day running of the SIG, the SIG committee will be formed of those currently active in this field of interest. This will be subject to the CAA steering committee's approval.

SIG Coordinators & Members

The groups coordinators are formed by those who are demonstratively active in this arena, while all CAA members are welcome to contribute to the group.

Speaker: n/a (I, Florian, can do that if the group is fine with it)

Group Coordinators

Name	Institute	Interests
Ethan Gruber	American Numismatic Society (USA)	LOD, Numismatics
Florian Thiery	Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum (Germany)	LOD, CIDOC, Wikidata
Karsten Tolle	University of Frankfurt (Germany)	LOD, Numismatics
Martina Trognitz	Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften (Austria)	LOD, Wikidata
Valeria Vitale	Institute of Classical Studies (GB)	LOD, Pelagios, Gazetteers
David Wigg-Wolf	Römisch-Germanische Kommission des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts (Germany)	LOD, Numismatics

Members

Name	Institute	Interests
John Muccigrosso	Drew University	LOD
Kai-Christian Bruhn	Hochschule Mainz (Germany)	LOD

others you have in mind?

Interested People without LOD knowledge (for Basics etc.)

Name	Institute	Interests
Dr. Gary Nobles	Koç University (Turkey)	LOD

others you have in mind?